

DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTERIZATION OF BILAYER TABLET FOR OPTIMIZED DRUG DELIVERY

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Abstract:

The present study was aimed at the development and characterization of a bilayer tablet of diclofenac sodium for optimized drug delivery. The formulation was designed to provide an immediate release (IR) layer for rapid onset of action and a sustained release (SR) layer for prolonged therapeutic effect. Bilayer tablets were prepared by the direct compression method using suitable excipients and polymers. The prepared tablets were evaluated for pre-compression parameters, physical characteristics, hardness, friability, drug content uniformity, and in vitro drug release studies. The IR layer showed 98.13% drug release within 30 minutes, indicating prompt drug availability, while the SR layer exhibited 97.28% drug release over an extended duration, demonstrating effective controlled release behavior. All evaluated parameters were found to be within acceptable limits, confirming good tablet integrity and uniformity. The results indicate that the developed bilayer tablet of diclofenac sodium is a promising approach for achieving optimized drug delivery with improved therapeutic efficacy and patient compliance.

Keywords: Bilayer tablet Diclofenac sodium Immediate release; Sustained release; Direct compression

I. INTRODUCTION

Oral route of drug administration is the most important method of administering drugs for systemic effects. Nevertheless, it is probable that at least 90 % of all drugs for systemic effects are administered by the oral route. When a new drug is discovered, one of the first questions a pharmaceutical company asks is whether or not the drug can be effectively administered for its intended effect for the oral route. If patient self-administration cannot be achieved, the sale of the drug constitutes only a small fraction of what the market would be otherwise of drugs that are administered orally, solid oral dosage forms represent the preferred class of product. Tablets and capsules represent unit dosage forms in which one usual dose of the drug has been accurately placed.^[1]

Nowadays various developed and developing countries are moving towards combination therapy for treatment of various diseases and disorders requiring long term therapy such as hypertension, Diabetes and Rheumatoid arthritis. The problem of dose dependent side effects is minimized by combination therapies and is advantageous over mono therapy from last few years; interest in developing a combination of two or more active pharmaceutical ingredients in a single dosage form has increased in pharmaceutical industry. Bi-layer tablets can be a primary option to avoid incompatibilities between APIs by physical separation.

Bi-layer tablet is suitable for sequential release of two drugs in combination, separate two incompatible substances and also for sustained release tablet in which one layer is immediate release as initial dose and second layer is maintenance dose. There are various applications of the bi-layer tablet as it consists of monolithic partially coated or multilayered matrices. Bi-layer tablets are tablets, made by compressing two different granulations fed into a die succession, one on top of another, in layers. Each layer comes from a separate feed frame with individual weight control. Rotary tablet press can be set up for two layers. More layers are possible but the design becomes very special. Bi-layer tablets are composed of two layers of granulation compressed together. They have the appearance of a sandwich because the edges of each layer are exposed.^[2]

The goal in designing sustained or controlled delivery systems is to reduce frequency of dosing or to increase effectiveness of the drug by localization at the site of action reducing the dose required or providing informed drug delivery. The primary objective of sustained release delivery is to insure safety and to improve efficacy of drugs as well as patient compliance.^[3]

Figure No.1 General Concept of Bilayer Tablet

Fig.No.2 Schematic presentation for compression of bi-layer tablet^[5]

Fig No.3 Drug release mechanism from bi layer tablet

FigNo.04 Showing immediate drug release from IR layer in stomach

Need of Developing Bilayer Tablet ^[7]

- For the administration of fixed dose combinations of different APIs, prolong the drug product life cycle buccal / mucoadhesive delivery systems fabricate novel drug delivery system such as chewing device and floating tablets for gastro-retentive drug delivery.
- Controlling the delivery rate of either single or two different active pharmaceutical ingredients.
- To modify the total surface area available for API layer either by sandwiching with one or two in active layers in order to achieve swellable/erodible barriers for modified release.
- To separate incompatible Active pharmaceutical ingredient (APIs) from each other, to control the release of API from one layer by utilizing the functional property of the other layer (such as, osmotic property).

General properties of bi-layer tablet dosage forms ^[8, 9]

- It should have graceful product identity free of defects like chips. Cracks. Discoloration and contamination.
- Should have sufficient strength to with stand mechanical shock during its production, packaging, shipping and dispensing.
- Should have physical and chemical stability.
- The bi - layer tablet must release drug in an expectable and reproducible manner.
- Must have a chemical stability shelf life, so as not to follow alteration of the medicinal agents

Various Techniques for Bilayer Tablet ^[10, 11, 12]

- **Various Approaches Used In the Bilayer Tablet** [14, 15, 16, 17]
- **Floating Drug Delivery System**
- From the formulation and technological point of view, the floating drug delivery systems are considerably easy and logical approach in the development of Gastro retentive dosage Forms (GRDFs)
- **Approaches to design Floating Drug Delivery System**
- The following approaches have been used for the design of floating dosage forms of single And multiple-unit systems.
- **Intra gastric bilayered floating tablets**
- These are also compressed table t as shown in figure and contain two layers i.e. Immediate and sustained release.
- **Multiple unit type floating pills**
- These systems consist of sustained release pills as ‘seeds’ surrounded by double layers. The inner layer consists of effervescent agents while the outer layer is of swellable membrane layer. When the system is immersed in dissolution medium at body temperature,
- it sinks at once and then forms swollen pills like balloons, which float as they have lower density.
- **Polymeric Bio adhesive System**
- These are designed to imbibe fluid following administration such that the outer layer becomes a viscous, tacky material that adheres to the gastric mucosa/mucus layer. This should encourage gastric retention until the adhesive forces are weakened. These are prepared as one layer with immediate dosing and other layer with bio adhesive property.
- **Swelling System**
- These are designed to be sufficiently small on administration so as not to make ingestion of the dosage form difficult (eg. less than approximately 23 mm long and less than 11 mm wide for an oval or capsule shaped tablet whereas 10- 12mm in diameter for round tablets). On ingestion they rapidly swell or disintegrate or unfold to a size that precludes passage through the pylorus until after drug release has progressed to a required degree. Gradual erosion of the system or its breakdown into smaller particles enables it to leave stomach. The simple bilayer tablet may contain an immediate release layer with the other layer as extended release or conventional release.

- **Bilayer Tablets:-**
- Bilayer tablets are composed of two or three layers of granulation compressed together. They have the appearance of a sandwich because the edges of each layer are exposed. Bi-layer tablet is suitable for sequential release of two drugs in combination, separate two incompatible substances and also for sustained release tablet in which one layer is immediate release as initial dose and second layer is maintenance dose.
- **Immediate Release Dosage Form:-** [22, 23, 24, 25]
- Immediate release tablets are those which disintegrate rapidly and get dissolved to release the medicaments. Immediate release may be provided for by way of an appropriate pharmaceutically acceptable diluents or carrier, which diluents or carrier does not prolong, to an appreciable extent, the rate of drug release and or absorption.” release of drug. The term “release” includes the presentation of the drug from the formulation in to the GIT, to body tissues and into the systemic circulation. For GIT release, the release is under pH conditions such as pH=1-3. The formulation of invention may release

at least 70% (preferably 80%) of active ingredient within 4 hours, such as within 3 hours, preferably 2 hours, more preferably within 1.5 hours, and especially within an hour (within 30 minutes) of administration, whether it may be oral or parenteral.

- **Desired Criteria for Immediate Release Drug Delivery System:-**

Immediate release dosage form should-

- In the case of solid dosage form it should dissolve or disintegrate in the stomach within a short period.
- In the case of liquid dosage form it should be compatible with taste masking.
- It should be portable without fragility concern.
- Should have a pleasing mouth feel.
- It shouldn't leave minimal or no residue in the mouth after oral administration.
- Exhibit low sensitivity to environmental condition such as humidity and temperature.
- It should be able to manufacture using conventional processing and packaging equipment at low cost.
- Rapid dissolution and absorption of drug, which may produce quick onset of action.

- **Sustained Release Dosage Forms: - ^[26]**

- Any drug or dosage form modification that prolongs the therapeutic activity of the drug. The release of the drug is retarded for a delayed and prolonged period of time in the systemic circulation. Sustained release formulation maintains a uniform blood level of drug with better patient compliance as well as increased efficacy of drug. Sustained release tablets are generally taken once or twice a day during a course of treatment whereas in conventional dosage forms there is need to take 3-4 times dosage in a day to achieve the same therapeutic action.

- **Rational for developing of SRDDS**

- Formulation of SRDDS minimizes dosing frequency and sustained release provides availability of a drug at action site throughout the treatment to improve clinical efficiency of a drug molecule.
- To reduce cost of treatment by reducing number of dosage requirement.
- To minimize toxicity due to overdose which is often in conventional dosage form.
- To enhance the activity duration of a drug possessing short half-life.

- **Physicochemical and pharmacokinetic parameters for drug selection ^[27]**

Physicochemical parameter for drug selection	Criteria for drug selection
Molecular size	< 1000 Daltons
Aqueous Solubility	More than 0.1 mg/ml for pH 1 to pH 7.8
Apparent partition coefficient	High
Absorption mechanism	Diffusion
General absorbability from all GI segments	Release Should not be influenced by pH and enzymes

Pharmacokinetic parameters for drug selection	Criteria for drug selection
Elimination half-life ($t_{1/2}$)	Between 2 to 8 hours
Absolute bioavailability	Should be 75% or more
Absorption rate constant (K_a)	Must be higher than release rate
Apparent volume of distribution (V_d)	Larger V_d and MEC, Larger will be the required dose.
Total clearance	Not depend on dose
Elimination rate constant	Required for design
Therapeutic concentration (C_{ss})	The lower C_{ss} and smaller V_d , the loss among of drug required.
Toxic concentration	Apart the value of MTC And MEC safer the dosage form.

(Fig.) Graphically representation of plasma concentrations of a conventional Immediate Release (IR), a Sustained Release (SR) and an idealized zero-order controlled release (ZOOCR) drug delivery systems. ^[28]

• **Criteria to be met by drug proposed to be formulated in sustained release dosage forms.** ^[29]

- a) Desirable half-life.
- b) High therapeutic index.
- c) Small dose.
- d) Desirable absorption and solubility characteristics.
- e) Desirable absorption window.
- f) First past clearance.

• **Factors Influencing Sustained Release Drug Delivery System** ^[32]

I. Physicochemical factor

- a) Aqueous Solubility
- b) Partition coefficient
- c) Drug Stability
- d) Protein Binding
- e) Drug pKa & Ionization at Physiological pH
- f) Mechanism and Site of Absorption
- g) Molecular size and diffusivity
- h) Dose size

II. Biological Factor

- a) Absorption
- b) Distribution
- c) Metabolism
- d) Half-life of Drug
- e) Margin of safety:

• **EXPERIMENTAL WORK**

• **Preformulation Study** ^(67, 68)

Preformulation can be defined investigation of physical and chemical properties drug substance alone and when combined with excipients. Preformulation studies are the first step in the rational development of dosage form of drug substance. The objectives of preformulation studies are to develop a portfolio of information about the drug substance so that this information is useful to develop formulation. Preformulation investigations are designed to identify those physicochemical properties and excipients that may influence the formulation design, method of manufacture and pharmacokinetic - biopharmaceutical properties of the resulting product.

The goals of the program therefore are:

- ❖ To establish the necessary physicochemical characteristics of a new drug substance.
- ❖ To determine its kinetic release rate profile.
- ❖ To establish its compatibility with different excipients. Hence, a preformulation study on the obtained sample of drug includes physical test determination and compatibility studies

- **Organoleptic properties** ⁽⁶⁹⁾

The drug powder was analyzed for colour, odour and taste.

- **Descriptions** ⁽⁶⁹⁾

The drug sample was analyzed for physical appearance and powder nature.

- **Melting points** ⁽⁶⁹⁾

Melting point of the drug sample was determined because it is a good first indication of purity of the sample since the presence of relatively small amount of impurity can be detected by a lowering as well as widening in the melting point range. Melting point of the drug was determined by taking a small amount of drug in a capillary tube closed at one end and it was placed in melting point apparatus veego (VMP) and the temperature at which the drug melts was noted. Average of triplicate readings was taken.

- **Solubility Analysis** ⁽⁶⁹⁾

The Solubility of the selected drug was determined in ethanol, Distilled water, and Methanol by the following procedure. The solubility analysis was also done to select a suitable solvent system to dissolve the drug and also to test its solubility in the dissolution medium was to be used.

Procedure

Excess amount of drug was taken in a 5ml of the solvent system. Stir it for 30 minutes. Keep it on a shaker for 48 hrs to achieve equilibrium and centrifuge it for 10 minutes, the supernatant layer is then filtered out. The dilutions are made from 5-50 ml and the solubility is determined by measuring the UV absorption.

- **Spectroscopic Studies**

- **Determination of λ max** ^(70,71)

Stock solution (100 μ g/ml) of Diclofenac sodium was prepared in methanol. The solution was kept in a cuvette. The UV spectrum was recorded in the range of 200-400 nm on UV- visible spectrophotometer.

- **FT-IR Spectrum Interpretation** ^(70, 71)

The infrared absorption spectrum of pure Diclofenac sodium was recorded on FT-IR spectrophotometer (Model-8400S, Shimadzu, Japan) and the spectrum analysis was done for functional groups. The FT-IR spectra of drug with excipient were compared with the standard FT-IR spectrum of the pure drug.

- **Preparation of Standard Calibration Curve of Diclofenac sodium** ^(70, 71)

The 50mg of diclofenac sodium is dissolved in 50 ml of Distilled water in volumetric flask and solution of different concentration were prepared like 2,4,6,8, and 10 μ g/ml and absorbance was taken at 276 nm using UV-visible spectrophotometer. Plot graph between Conc.vs. Abs. Calculate coefficient of correlation should between (0.9-1) & slope.

- **Preparation of Immediate Release and Sustained Release Layer of Diclofenac Sodium**

I. Preparation of Immediate Release Layer by Direct Compression Method.

^(72, 73)

The immediate release layer prepared by direct compression method according to the formula given in table. All the ingredients weighed are mixed in geometrical order. The ingredients were passed through 60# mesh sieve and the sifted drug, and super disintegrating agent were accurately weighed and transferred in to porcelain mortar and mixed up to 30 min for uniform mixing. Then add other excipient to above mixture. Finally add glidant in to the blend and mixed for 2 min. direct compression done by using a 7 mm round flat- punch of a rotary tablet machine.

II. Preparation of Sustained Release Layer by Direct Compression Method.

Sustained release tablet layer was prepared by direct compression method according to the formula given in table. All the ingredients including drug were weighed accurately and passed through 60# mesh sieve separately. The drug and polymers like HPMC K100M, HPMC K15 M was mixed by small portion of both each time and blend it to get a uniform mixture and kept aside. Then all the ingredients weighed are mixed in geometrical order excluding magnesium stearate and talc to get a uniform blend. Finally mixture is blended with magnesium stearate and tablets were compressed by using a 7 mm round flat-punch of a rotary tablet machine.

III. Compression of Bilayer Tablet

Optimized batch of Immediate Release and Sustained Release Layer was selected for formulation of the bilayer tablet. As a previously reported procedure, the powder blend of Immediate Release and Sustained Release Layer were prepared separately. Initially the powder blend of a sustained release layer was filled in the die cavity of the rotary tablet machine and compressed one time by giving a single rotation, then the immediate release layer was filled over the sustained release compressed layer and both layers were compressed to form bilayer tablet through direct compression by using the 7 mm round flat-punch of the rotary tablet machine.

Table No. Formulation of Immediate Release Layer (mg/Tablet)

Ingredients	IR1	IR2	IR3	IR4
Diclofenac sodium	25	25	25	25
Crosspovidone	2	3	2	3
Croscarmellose	2	3	3	2
Lactose	50	50	50	50
M.C.C	24	22	23	23
Mag .stearate	1	1	1	1
Sunset yellow	1	1	1	1
Total weight	105	105	105	105

Table No. Formulation of Sustained Release Layer (mg/Tablet)

Ingredients	SR1	SR2	SR3	SR4	SR5	SR6	SR7	SR8	SR9
Diclofenac sodium	75	75	75	75	75	75	75	75	75
HPMC K100M	15	15	10	15	5	10	10	5	5
HPMC K15M	15	10	15	5	15	10	5	10	5
Lactose	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
Talc	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
MCC	30	35	35	40	40	40	45	45	50
Mag. stearate	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Total weight	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195

- **Evaluation of Tablet**
- **Pre-Compression Parameter** ^(74, 75, 76)

➤ **Bulk Density**

The loose bulk density was obtained by dividing the mass of powder by the bulk volume in cm³. The 10gm sample was carefully introduced into a 25ml graduated cylinder. The volume occupied by the powder was recorded and bulk density then calculated. It was calculated by using equation given below:

$$D_f = M/V_p$$

Where,

D_f = Loose bulk density

M = Weight of samples in grams

V_p = Final volumes of granules in cm³

➤ **Tapped Density (Dt)**

The tapped bulk density was obtained by dividing the mass of a powder by the tapped volume in cm³. The 10gm sample was carefully introduced into a 25ml graduated cylinder. The cylinder was dropped at 2-second intervals onto a hard wood surface 100 times from a height of 1 inch. The tapped bulk density of each formulation was then obtained by dividing the weight of sample in grams by the final tapped volume in cm³ of the sample contained in the cylinder. It was calculated by using equation given below:

$$D_o = M/ V_p$$

Where,

D_o = Tapped bulk density.

M = Weight of samples in grams.

V_p = Final tapped volumes of granules in cm³.

➤ **Compressibility Index and Hausner ratio**

In recent years, the compressibility index and the closely related Hausner ratio have become the simple, fast and popular methods of predicting powder flow characteristics. The compressibility index has been proposed as an indirect measure of bulk density, size and shape, surface area, moisture content and cohesiveness of materials because all of these can influence the observed compressibility index. The compressibility index and the Hausner ratio are determined by measuring both the bulk density and the tapped density of a powder.

$$\% \text{ Compressibility} = \frac{pt-p_0}{pt} \times 100$$

Where,

Po = Bulk density,

Pt =Tapped Density.

➤ **Hausner Ratio**

$$\text{Hausner ratio} = \frac{pt}{po}$$

Where,

Pt =Tapped Density.

Po = Bulk density

Table : Relationship between % Compressibility and flowability

Compressibility index %	Flow property	Hausner Ratio
≤10	Excellent	1.00 -1.11
11-15	Good	1.12-1.18
16-20	Fair	1.19-1.25
21-25	Passable	1.26-1.34
26-31	Poor	1.35-1.45
32-37	Very poor	1.46.1.59
>38	Very, very poor	>1.60

➤ **Angle of Repose**

The angle of repose has been used to characterize the flow properties of solid. Angle of repose is a characteristic related to interparticulate friction or resistance to movement between particles. This is the maximum angle possible between surface of pile of powder or granules and the horizontal plane.

$$\tan \theta = h / r$$

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} h/r$$

Where,

θ = Angle of repose

h = Height

r = Radius

A funnel was fixed at a height approximately of 2 cm over the platform. The loose powder was slowly passed along the wall of funnel, till the cone of the powder formed. Determined the Angle of repose by measuring the height of the cone of powder and radius of the heap of powder.

Table No: Relation between angle of (θ) and flowability

Angle of Repose (θ)	Flowability
< 25	Excellent
25 – 30	Good
30 – 40	Moderate flow
> 40	Very poor

- **Post compression parameter**

- **Hardness test** ^(77,78)

Although hardness test is not an official, tablet should have sufficient handling during packing and transportation. Hardness of tablet was measured by using Monsanto hardness tester. It is the pressure required to fracture diametrically placed tablets by applying the force. The hardness of 3 tablets, from each batch was determined and mean hardness was taken into account, which was expressed in kg/cm².

- **Friability test**

Friability test is performed to assess the effect of friction and shocks, which may often cause tablet to chip, or break. Roche friabilator was used for purpose. This device subjects a number of tablets to the combined effects of abrasion and shock by utilizing a plastic chamber that revolves at 25 rpm dropping the tablets at distance of 6 inches with each revolution. Preweight sample of tablets was placed in the friabilator, which was then opened for 100 revolutions. Tablets were deducted and reweight. Compressed tablets should not loose more than 1 % of their weight.

The percentage friability was measured using following formula

$$\% \text{Friability} = \frac{(\text{initial weight} - \text{final weight}) \times 100}{(\text{Initial weight})}$$

- **Weight variation test** ^(77,78)

Weighing 20 tablets individually, calculating the average weight and compressing the individual tablets weight to average weight to the average USP weight variation test. The table no given below shows the weight variation tolerance for uncoated tablets.

Table No: Weight variation tolerance for tablets.

Average weight of tablets (mg)	Maximum % deviation allowed
130mg or less	10%
130mg to 324 mg	7.5%
More than 324 mg	5%

- **Thickness**

The thickness of the tablet was measured using venire caliper. Thickness of 3 tablets from each batch was measured and mean was calculated.

- **Drug Content uniformity** ⁽⁷⁹⁾

Five tablets were weighed individually, and these tablets were crushed in a mortar. Drug equivalent to 10 mg of powder was taken, to this 100 ml of distilled water was added. The absorbance was measured at 276 nm after suitable dilution using double beam UV visible spectrophotometer. The drug content was determined.

- **Disintegration test** ⁽⁸⁰⁾

Disintegration test is a method to evaluate the rate of disintegration of tablets. It is also defined as break down of solid dosage form into smaller particles when it is disintegrated. Place 1 tablet in each of 6 tubes and added a disc of each tube. Maintain the temperature of the disintegration media at 37[±] 2 as specified in the monographs. At the end of time limit specified, left the basket from fluid and observe the tablets.

- **In-vitro Dissolution Studies** ^(81,82)

The In vitro dissolution study for the Diclofenac sodium sustained release tablets were carried out in USP type-I dissolution test apparatus using 900 ml of dissolution medium at 50 rpm and temperature 37±0.5 °C. the tablet were placed in the pH 1.2 (0.1 N HCL)(simulated gastric fluid pH) for 2 hrs and pH 7.5 for 12 hrs .then the apparatus was run at 37±0.5 °C .and a rotating speed of 50 rpm in a 900 ml dissolution medium. The 5ml aliquots were withdrawn at intervals of 5,10,15,20,25,30, minutes 1 hour 2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12, hour and replacement was done each time with equal amount of fresh dissolution medium maintained at same tempreature.each 5ml of sample was withdraw and diluted with (pH1.2) 0.1 N HCL for first 2 hours and then with 7.5 pH phosphate buffer for next 12 hours each 5ml aliquots filtered through Whatmann filter paper (No.41) and absorbance was measured at 276nm using UV spectrophotometer. Drug concentration in the sample was determined from standard calibration curve. Then calculate amount and % drug release.

- **Model fitting** ^(83, 84, 85)

The model fitting for percent cumulative release was done using PCP Disso software to find the best fitted kinetic equation for the dissolution profile.

- **Kinetics of drug release**

In order to understand the mechanism and kinetics of drug release, the results of the in-vitro dissolution study of the optimized batch was fitted with various kinetic equations like.

- ❖ Zero order (% Release =Kt),
- ❖ First order (log % Unreleased =Kt),
- ❖ Higuchi's model (% Release =Kt^{0.5}) and
- ❖ Pappas Korsmeyer equation (% Release=Ktⁿ)
- ❖ (or) Empirical equation (Power law expression) of

$$M_t / M_\infty = K t^n$$

Where,

M. Amount of drug release at time t

M_e - Amount of drug release at infinite time

K- Constant characteristics, and

n- Diffusional exponent

If n= 0.5 indicates Fickian diffusion mechanism (Higuchi matrix)

n =0.5 to 1 indicates Anomalous Transport or Non Fickian transport.

n =1 indicates Case II Transport (Zero order release)

n > 1 indicates Super case -II transport

Coefficient of correlation (R²) values were calculated for the linear curves obtained by regression analysis of the above plots.

Table No.: The Value of 'n' characterize the release mechanism of drug by korsmeyer Peppas kinetic model

Diffusion exponents(n)	Diffusion mechanism	Type of dosage form	Release mechanism
Fickian diffusion	0.45 ≤ n	Non swelling matrices	Fickian diffusion
Anomalous (non-Fickian) diffusion	0.45 < n < 0.89	swelling matrices	Non-Fickian
Case-II transport	n = 0.89	Swelling and erodible matrices	Zero order kinetics
Super case-II transport	n > 0.89	Swelling and erodible matrices	Zero order kinetics

To find out the exponents n from the portion of the release curve, where $M_t / M_\infty < 0.6$ to study the release kinetics, data obtained from in vitro drug release plotted as log cumulative percentage drug release versus log time.

➤ **Accelerated Stability Study** ⁽⁸⁶⁾

In any rationale design and evaluation of dosage forms for drugs, the stability of the active component must be major criteria in determining their acceptance or rejection.

During the stability studies the product is exposed to normal conditions of temperature and humidity. However the studies will take a longer time and hence it would be convenient to carry out the accelerated stability studies where the product is stored under extreme conditions of temperature. In the present study, stability studies were carried out on optimized formulation. The tablet were stored at $40 \pm 2^\circ C / 75 \pm 5\% RH$ for duration of 45 days, sample was withdrawn and tested for drug entrapment, and drug release study.

The reasons for stability studies:

- There may be chemical degradation of the active drug leading to a substantial lowering of the quantity of the therapeutic agent in the dosage form.
- Although chemical degradation of the active drug may not be extensive, a toxic product may be formed in the decomposition procedure.
- Instability of a drug product can lead to a decrease in its bioavailability. This can lead to a substantial lowering in the therapeutic efficiency of the dosage form.

- **RESULT AND DISCUSSION**

- **Preformulation Results of selected Drug:-**

Organoleptic characterization and Melting point Determination

Sr.No	Test	Observation
1	Colour	White To Off-White
2	Odour	Odorless
3	Taste	Bitter
4	Melting point	283-285 °C

The organoleptic character and melting point was found to be as per standard drug so used in the formulation was found to be pure according to IP specification.

- **Solubility Analysis :-**

Solubility profile of Diclofenac sodium

Sr.No	Solvent	Solubility
1	Distilled water	Sparingly soluble
2	Glacial acetic acid	Sparingly soluble
3	Methanol	Freely soluble
4	Ethanol	Freely soluble
5	Ether	Insoluble
6	Chloroform	Insoluble

- **UV Spectroscopic studies**

Determination of λ max for diclofenac sodium

Diclofenac sodium showed the maximum wavelength at 276 nm, which matches with the standard. Hence drug used in formulation was found to be pure according to I.P specification.

Fig : λ max of Diclofenac sodium

- **FTIR Study of Diclofenac Sodium**

IR spectrum recorded using FTIR spectrophotometer there is no change in the peak of FTIR spectra of drug, when correlated with FTIR spectra of drug given in I.P.

Hence drug used in the formulation was found to be pure according to I.P. specification.

The spectrum of diclofenac sodium showed an intense, well defined peak, infrared band at around 1602.85 cm⁻¹ (C=C) and 3203.76 cm⁻¹ (COOH carboxylic acid) peak and 3387.00 cm⁻¹ (N- H amine) peaks .

Fig : IR spectra of Diclofenac Sodium

Fig . IR spectra of HPMC

Fig no. IR spectra of Diclofenac sodium + HPMC

- Standard Calibration curve of Diclofenac sodium in Distilled water

Table:

Sr. No	Concentration (µg/ml)	ABSORBANCE AT 276 NM
1.	0	0
2.	2	0.2470
3.	4	0.2575
4.	6	0.4341
5.	8	0.6972
6.	10	0.9798

Correlation of coefficient (R^2) = 0.922
Equation of regressed line; $Y=0.095x-0.048$

Table : Precompression evaluation parameters for Immediate release layer of Diclofenac sodium

Formulation	Bulk Density (g/cm ³)	Tapped Density (g/cm ³)	Carr's Index (%)	Hausner Ratio	Angle of Repose (degrees)
IR1	0.536 ± 0.02	0.525±0.01	10.0%	1.11	29.1±0.02
IR2	0.520 ± 0.02	0.552±0.02	12.2%	1.14	29.8±0.01
IR3	0.510 ±0.04	0.567±0.04	12.1%	1.14	30.5±0.01
IR4	0.507±0.04	0.559±0.03	12.4%	1.13	31.6±0.03

Each sample was analyzed in triplicate (n=3)

Powder of immediate release diclofenac sodium tablets show angle of repose (< 33) indicate good flow properties of the powder, Carr's index (< 20) indicate good flow properties.

Table : Post compression evaluation parameters for Immediate release layer of Diclofenac sodium

Formulation	Thickness (mm)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Disintegration Time (min)	Weight variation (mg)	Friability (%)	Drug content (%)
IR1	2.23	3.5	3.60	105.5	0.43	93.30
IR2	2.22	3.7	2.90	104.0	0.51	99.90
IR3	2.20	3.6	3.70	104.5	0.56	95.80
IR4	2.30	4.0	3.90	106.0	0.49	97.80

Table : Precompression evaluation parameters for Sustained release layer of Diclofenac sodium

Formulation	Bulk Density (g/cm ³)	Tapped Density (g/cm ³)	Carr's Index (%)	Hausner Ratio	Angle of Repose (degrees)
SR1	0.443 ±0.013	0.508±0.008	12.6	1.14	29.93 ± 0.18
SR2	0.466 ±0.009	0.528±0.017	11.7	1.13	29.65 ± 0.09
SR3	0.488±0.007	0.522±0.019	7.89	1.06	29.30 ± 0.18
SR4	0.455 ±0.011	0.495±0.013	8.68	1.08	29.56 ± 0.18
SR5	0.469 ±0.014	0.506±0.007	8.41	1.07	31.02 ±0.014
SR6	0.434 ±0.008	0.498±0.021	11.35	1.14	29.75±0.011
SR7	0.405±0.01	0.468±0.01	13.4	1.16	31.0 ± 0.01
SR8	0.399±0.02	0.462±0.02	13.6	1.16	34.7 ± 0.01
SR9	0.408±0.01	0.472±0.01	13.5	1.16	31.5 ± 0.02

Each sample was analyzed in triplicate (n=3)

The result of angle of repose (<30) indicate good flow properties of the sustained release powder .This was further supported by lower Carr's index values. Carr's index values up to 20% result in good to excellent flow properties. All the drug and excipient were found good to excellent properties.

Table : Post compression evaluation parameters for Sustained release layer of Diclofenac sodium

Formulation	Thickness (mm)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Weight variation (mg)	Friability (%)	Drug content (%)
SR1	4.40	5.0	196.5	0.58	89.93
SR2	4.30	4.5	198	0.52	91.24
SR3	4.20	5.2	195.5	0.49	93.66
SR4	4.10	4.5	200	0.43	93.73
SR5	4.01	4.3	201	0.51	92.38
SR6	3.92	4.2	196.5	0.56	97.28
SR7	3.92	4.5	194.5	0.45	94.82
SR8	3.97	4.7	198	0.55	90.11
SR9	4.01	4.5	196	0.56	89.95

• **Cumulative Percent drug release from Immediate release layer**

Time (min)	Cumulative percent drug release (%)			
	IR1	IR2	IR3	IR4
5	22.93	20.10	24.13	20.79
10	30.45	30.17	46.61	35.15
15	39.45	50.47	55.15	49.23
20	52.23	65.20	60.23	57.45
25	70.35	82.53	79.35	69.39
30	80.42	98.13	92.42	82.40

• **Cumulative Percent drug release from Sustained release layer**

Time (hr)	Cumulative percent drug release (%)								
	SR1	SR2	SR3	SR4	SR5	SR6	SR7	SR8	SR9
1	16.43	28.36	18.15	21.78	19.12	20.14	19.25	18.20	20.12
2	20.82	32.86	25.15	26.19	28.37	31.24	29.40	24.12	29.45
3	37.26	36.86	39.13	35.64	35.48	42.14	35.50	30.42	35.61
4	40.46	37.11	45.15	39.15	46.8	45.56	49.76	35.20	40.81
5	42.39	39.87	50.67	49.95	53.90	47.96	59.43	45.13	45.18
6	44.13	40.72	59.34	55.40	60.22	52.53	67.54	54.87	55.21
7	46.45	55.64	62.55	60.22	61.80	54.43	69.20	61.98	63.20
8	48.56	60.25	65.78	66.20	65.70	56.34	71.45	66.35	67.81
9	53.63	65.15	70.65	72.55	77.51	65.35	75.65	70.13	75.45
10	60.94	71.96	75.60	80.24	78.60	79.81	80.15	76.89	79.23
11	70.98	76.31	80.45	85.20	82.57	90.67	86.54	80.23	82.43
12	78.14	83.86	85.83	88.20	90.52	97.66	91.87	85.20	87.92

Fig. No. In vitro dissolution profile IR1, IR2, IR3, and IR4 formulation

Fig. In vitro dissolution profile SR1, SR2, and SR3 Formulation

Fig : In vitro dissolution profile SR4, SR5, SR6, Formulation

Fig No. In vitro dissolution profile SR7, SR8, SR9, Formulation

• Discussion

Preformulation study of the IR batches are shown in the Table . where bulk density in the range of 0.5-0.53 gm/ml, tapped density shown in the range of 0.5/0.56gm/ml, car's index is 10-13, hausner ratio was 1.1, angle of repose is 29°-33° and disintegration time was 10-15 min. The Drug release of IR2 trial was found almost similar to the theoretical profile as shown in table , and also it has the fast disintegration time as compare with other batches. So it has been concluded that the combination of concentration of the Croscarmellose sodium and crosspovidone is optimized as a disintegrants. Preformulation of the IR2 tablet has showed the good flow property among all other batch of the IR layer tablets. Also shown highest drug release 98.13% at 30 min which was selected further for the optimization of the bi-layer tablets.

The comparative dissolution profile of SR1-SR9 shown in table . Batch SR6 give maximum drug release 95.66% compare to SR1-SR9 batches, and it also give the same release profile as per dissolution profile as per USP. Optimized batch SR6 has passed all the specified range of parameter. Like weight variation, It has also sufficient hardness 4-5(kg/cm²) to stand mechanical shock, which was the optimized for the further study because less than the above value then the tablet layer become separated during the friability study. Friability of batch SR6 was found 0.56% which less than 1% and drug content was 97.28% desirable for our formulation. Therefore SR6 batch is considered optimized batch for the SR layer.

• Kinetic Modeling Data of Optimized Batch IR2 &SR6

The mathematical models are used to evaluate the kinetics and mechanism of drug release from the tablets. The model that best fits the release data is selected based on the correlation coefficient (r) value in various models. The model that gives high 'r' value is considered as the best fit of the release data. The optimized batch follows the higuchi plot.

Kinetic Modeling Data of Optimized Batch

Table No.

R ²				
Zero Order	First Order	Hixon Crowell	korse meyer peppas model	Higuchi Plot
0.9734	0.6986	0.8713	0.5698	0.9909

• Accelerated stability study

The stability studies were carried out as per ICH guidelines on optimized formulations. The formulations were stored at 40 ± 2°C/75 ± 5 % RH for 90 days. After 90 days the samples were withdrawn and retested for thickness, hardness, drug content, in-vitro drug release studies.

Table : Parameters studies of Bilayer tablet on optimized batch IR2 & SR6 before and after stability study.

Sr.No.	Parameters	Observation	
		Before	After
1	Hardness	7.7±0.4kg/cm ²	7.6±0.2kg/cm ²
2	Friability	0.52±04%	0.52±04%
3	Thickness	6.14±0.04 mm	6.14±0.01mm
4	Weight variation	302.5±0.01	302.5±0.01
5	Disintegration time	2 min 90 sec	2 min 90 sec
6	Drug content	97.66 %	96.34%

TABLE NO: CUMULATIVE PERCENT DRUG RELEASE OF OPTIMIZED FORMULATION BEFORE AND AFTER STABILITY STUDY.

Time (min)	(Hr)	Observation			
		Before stability study	After 30 Days	After 60 Days	After 90 Days
0		0	0	0	0
5	-	16.2	16.43	28.36	18.15
10	-	23.21	20.82	32.86	25.15
15	-	25.12	37.26	36.86	39.13
30	-	28.34	40.46	37.11	45.15
-	1	34.6	42.39	39.87	50.67
-	2	39.2	44.13	40.72	59.34
-	3	45.87	46.45	55.64	62.55
-	4	52.65	48.56	60.25	65.78
-	5	59.43	53.63	65.15	70.65
-	6	65.76	60.94	71.96	75.6
-	7	77.51	74.98	76.31	80.45
-	8	80.54	78.14	79.86	81.83
-	9	84.57	83.19	82.15	84.21
-	10	89.67	88.2	87.3	86.2
-	11	92.32	91.66	90.12	89.11
-	12	97.66	96.2	94.6	92.65

Fig. No : In vitro Dissolution profile of formulation before and after stability study.

The stability study was carried out on optimized formulation IR2&SR6. The formulation was stored at $40 \pm 2^{\circ}C/75 \pm 5\%$ for 90 days. After 30, 60 and 90 days sample were withdrawn and retested for in vitro drug release studies, other parameters were checked after 90 days.

There were no considerable changes in physical parameters of tablet such as thickness, hardness, drug content and dissolution profile in table of bilayer tablet of formulation after accelerated stability study.

• Conclusion

It can be concluded that the immediate release and sustained release bilayer tablet of Diclofenac sodium for the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis, osteoarthritis and ankylosing spondylitis. It is also used in short term treatment of acute musculoskeletal injury, acute painful shoulder. Postoperative pain and dysmenorrhoea and myalgia, dental or minor surgical pain, postpartum pain, migraine and other types of headaches and fever prepare and reduces the side effect.

By using the polymer HPMC K 100M, HPMC K15M concluded that the increase the drug release of diclofenac sod. Up to 12hr. and super disintegrating agent crosscarmellose sod. and crosspovidone for immediate release up to 30 min. By formulating diclofenac sodium we can improve stability of formulation fixed dosing, increase patient compliance and also bioavailability of drug.

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